

Automatised and georeferenced energy assessment of an Antwerp district based on cadastral data

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ABSTRACT

Municipalities play a key role in supporting Europe's energy transition towards a low-carbon economy. However, there is a lack of tools to allow municipalities to easily formulate a detailed energy vision for their city. Nevertheless, most municipalities have access to georeferenced cartographic and cadastre information, including that on basic building characteristics. This article describes an innovative method to calculate and display the current hourly thermal energy demand for each building in a district based on basic cartography, cadastre, and degree-day values. The method is divided into two main blocks: (1) input data processing to obtain geometric information (e.g. geolocation, building and facades' dimensions) and semantic data (e.g. use, year of construction), and (2) district energy assessment to calculate the thermal energy demand using data obtained in block 1. The proposed method has been applied and tested in the historical district of Antwerp. The reliability and thoroughness of the results obtained using the method are demonstrated based on two different validations: (1) comparison of the results with those calculated using an existing dynamic energy simulation tool, and (2) comparison of the results with the real gas consumption of a partial sector of the selected district. The first validation shows that the average difference between the two methodologies is less than 11% for the heating demand, less than 11% for the cooling demand, and less than 15% for the domestic hot water demand. The second validation shows a 24% difference between the real natural gas consumption and that obtained by new methodology. Finally, the results have been presented to the municipality of Antwerp, which plans to use the method to design the district heating expansion within the city centre. Furthermore, sensitivity assessment was used to determine the relevance of the main input parameters considered in this method, such as the base temperature, energy system schedules, window-to-wall ratio, and solar gains.

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1. Introduction

Energy security and climate change are driving a future that will require significant improvements in the energy performance of the building sector. The 28 member states of the European Union (EU) have set an energy saving target of 30% to be reached by 2030 [1], mainly through energy efficiency measures. The EU also committed to a reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by 80–95% by 2050, as part of its roadmap for moving to a competitive low-carbon economy in 2050 [2]. Buildings are one of the world's largest energy-consuming sectors, accounting for nearly 30% of the global energy consumption and ~40% of the energy consumption

in the EU [3]. Municipalities play a key role in supporting Europe's energy transition towards a low-carbon economy. For example, thousands of local and regional authorities launched the Covenant of Mayors for Climate & Energy [4], which represents a voluntarily commitment to achieve EU climate and energy objectives on their territory. Other cities focused their effort on the design of environmental plans [5] or the development of regulations for building energy efficiency [6,7]. Therefore, municipality sensitivity and engagement are part of the day-to-day work of different public stakeholders.

Local authorities and municipalities maintain and manage various sources of information on the buildings in their municipality for the formulation of urban plans and public works. These few sources of information are generally heterogeneous, rarely related to each other, and sometimes only available on paper. One of the

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Nomenclature

$\Delta T_{i,j}$	temperature difference between the base temperature and the outside temperature (°C)
A_f	surface of the facade (m ²)
A_k	surface (m ²)
A_r	surface of the roof (m ²)
A_w	surface of the window (m ²)
ACD_k	annual cooling useful energy demand (kWh/year)
AHD_k	annual heating useful energy demand (kWh/year)
$CDH_{i,j}$	cooling degree-hours (°C)
CF_e	convective factor of equipment (%)
CF_l	convective factor of lighting (%)
CF_o	convective factor of occupancy (%)
$DHWD_k$	annual domestic hot water useful energy (kWh/year)
FTF_k	floor to floor height (m)
G_e	internal gains of equipment (W/m ²)
G_l	internal gains of lighting (W/m ²)
G_o	internal gains of occupancy (W/m ²)
$G_{s(i,j)}$	hourly internal solar gains (W/m ²)
GFA_k	gross floor area (m ²)
$HCD_{i,j}$	hourly cooling demand (kW)
$HDH_{i,j}$	heating degree-hours (°C)
$HHH_{i,j}$	hourly heating demand (kW)
HV_k	heated volume (m ³)
i	hour of the day
$IG_{i,j}$	internal gains (kW)
IP	input
j	day of the year
n_{HR}	heat recovery system efficiency (%)
N_k	number of air changes per hour
NF_k	number of floors
NHA_k	net heated area (m ²)
OP	output
$S_{e(i,j)}$	schedule of equipment
$S_{l(i,j)}$	schedule of lighting
$S_{o(i,j)}$	schedule of occupancy
$T_{b,C}$	cooling base temperature (°C)
$T_{b,H}$	heating base temperature (°C)
$TA_{i,j}$	outdoor air temperature (°C)
$TCL_{i,j}$	thermal conductivity losses (kW)
TIS_k	thickness of the internal slab (m)
U_f	thermal transmittance of the facade (W/(m ² K))
U_k	thermal transmittance (W/(m ² K))
U_r	thermal transmittance of the roof (W/(m ² K))
U_w	thermal transmittance of the window (W/(m ² K))
V_k	total volume of the building (m ³)
VL_k	ventilation losses (kW)

most widespread and interesting available information sources is the cadastre. The International Federation of Surveyors Statement on the Cadastre emphasises the relevance of the cadastre as a land information system for the social and economic development. It usually includes a geometric description of land parcels linked to other records describing the nature of the ownership or control of those interests and often the values of the parcel and its improvements. Boundaries of parcels can be defined by physical demarcation on the ground or by mathematical description, which is usually based on a coordinate system. There is no homogeneous cadastral model at the European level. However, although each country has its own structure, this information is available to all countries because it is the tool used to collect taxes.

This paper presents an innovative method that allows municipalities to carry out energy studies of their existing building stock using cadastral information. The paper shows how this method contributes to the solution of the following challenges and problems: 1) the lack of tools that allow an energy vision of an entire city, and 2) the availability of data needed to perform the energy assessment.

The paper is structured as follows: first, several related studies are discussed in Section 2. The methodology implemented into the District Mapping Module (DMM) is described in Section 3. A case study used to test the proposed solution is described in Section 4. The results are validated in Section 5 based on comparisons with dynamic energy simulations and real fuel consumption. A sensitivity and uncertainty evaluation is described in Section 6. Finally, the paper ends with conclusions and future work recommendations.

2. Related work

Depending on the desired detail or available input data, different methods can be used to carry out an energy evaluation in the construction sector. In the first approach, the information is taken from different existing databases [8–11] and the value of the energy demand of the buildings is estimated. Its simplicity allows to quickly perform general calculations. However, the precision of the results is low due to the generic demand values used in the calculation for each country. In the second approach, the demand is obtained by means of a stationary calculation [12]. To perform this type of calculation, it is necessary to know the characteristics of the building envelope elements: the thermal boundary of the heated zone, thermal transmittance, and climatic data of the area that will be defined based on heating and cooling degree days. Furthermore, this method allows the integration of aspects such as internal gains, ventilation losses, or solar gains. The accuracy of the results is considerably higher by this method compared to the simplified method. Finally, the third approach focuses on the use of specific software, such as Design Builder® [13], Energyplus [14], Transient System Simulation Tool [15] or Integrated Environmental Solutions [16], to perform dynamic simulations. In this case, it is necessary to enter a large amount of input data compared with the aforementioned methods, which makes its application difficult. However, the results are closer to the real building energy performance.

Furthermore, several tools have been developed over the past few years to facilitate the energy assessment of district and cities. For example, the Dynamic Energy Atlas tool enables the solution of energy issues related to both demand and production in a fully geographical context [17]. However, the outputs of this tool cannot be used in a decision-making process to assess the building energy performance and refurbishment strategies implementation because of the required input data, assessment scale, and top-down approach. Another interesting tool is the Neighbourhood Evaluation for Sustainable Territories (NEST), a plugin for Sketchup, which assesses the energy, environmental, economic, and social indicators [18]. It is important to mention that this tool includes a life-cycle approach and allows the 3D visualisation of the model. However, the direct use of the tool by municipalities remains difficult due to its main weaknesses (manual insertion of all building parameters, manual modelling of the district, and current limits of its scope to Spain and France). In addition, NEST still does not work in a Geographic Information System (GIS) environment. Another tool developed for building energy simulations at the district scale is CitySim [19]. In conjunction with other assessments, this tool simulates the energy demand of buildings, considering the stochastic nature of occupant presence and behaviour and a range of commonly used heating, ventilation, and air conditioning systems. However,

CitySim requires specific energy simulation knowledge and its own detailed XML input file to represent building information.

Other conceptually similar examples have been developed based on datasets containing basic cartographic and cadastral data available to the city administration with the aim of estimating the energy performance of buildings at the city scale. Within the framework of the 'EnerCity' project, a method was developed to obtain a city-wide energy map of the built environment. The method is based on a 3D city model generated from partially sub-optimal datasets [20]. However, the energy performance estimation focuses on residential buildings only and most of the working assumptions for the reduction of required data are based on Italian databases. The method automatically generates and simulates urban building energy models based on city GIS datasets for city-scale building energy retrofit analysis [21]. Design Builder® [13] is used for the estimation of the energy performance of the buildings. The required set of parameters of each building is quite large (45 characteristics), which is hard to find in datasets available for most of the cities. In addition, the modelling method requires a large amount of computing resources, which increases exponentially with the number of buildings included in the study area.

Finally, Braulio et al. [22] discussed several methods with the aim of energy assessment of building stocks in a literature review. They concluded that an appropriate methodology for the evaluation of the energy use of building stocks should be based on a bottom-up approach. Braulio et al. developed a bottom-up-based methodology for the prediction of the energy demand (heating and cooling) and discomfort hours of residential stocks at neighbourhood and city scales. The results obtained by this methodology are similar to that of this study, including cadastral data developed in a GIS environment, energy demand assessment, and so forth. However, the two main differences are the data source and energy assessment. Braulio's et al study is based on a sample building selection to develop the energy simulations by Energyplus [14]. However, the methodology proposed in this study is based on an hourly energy assessment of each building of the selected area. Additionally, the relevance of the data processing of the methodology defined in this study allows the automation of the whole assessment, simplifying the inputs and reducing the required technical knowledge of the end user. Finally, it is important to highlight that most of the studies analysed by Braulio et al. focused on residential buildings only, while the methodology defined in this study permits the assessment of nine different building uses.

Based on the conclusions of the review of different studies and tools, the proposed methodology has to fulfil following requirements: (A) base the assessment on cadastral data; (B) consider the geometry of the buildings; (C) use a non-dynamic energy system assessment; and (D) implementation in a GIS environment.

3. District mapping module method and assessment hypothesis

The European research project PlanHeat [23] will develop an integrated, easy-to-use, and open source tool, which will support local authorities in selecting, simulating, and comparing alternative low-carbon and economically sustainable scenarios for heating and cooling. The integrated PlanHeat tool will be designed to support municipalities in 1) mapping the potential of locally available low-carbon energy sources, 2) mapping the current and future demand for heating and cooling, 3) defining and simulating alternative supply scenarios, 4) understanding the interactions of these scenarios with existing infrastructures and networks, 5) identifying the potential for further extension and upgrade of district heating and cooling networks, and 6) evaluating the benefits by means of energy, economic, and environmental performance indicators.

The PlanHeat tool will be a platform that will allow the inter-connection of three open source modules: Mapping Module (at city

and district scale), Planning Module, and Simulation Module. This paper focuses on highlighting the characteristics of one submodule of the Mapping Module, which maps, quantifies, and stores the georeferenced, current thermal energy demand of each building at the district scale, that is, the District Mapping Module (DMM). The DMM is going to be a plugin for QGIS v. 3.0, a free and open-source GIS cross-platform application. This article presents the methodological basis and assessment hypothesis for the implementation of this module and its validation through a pilot case (Antwerp). Fig. 1 shows the general outline of the DMM in which the two main blocks are defined: Input Data block and District Energy Assessment (DEA) block. These two blocks will be described in the following sections. To generate energy demand profiles at the district scale, the DMM applies a 'bottom-up' method [24]. Based on this methodology, the DMM individually calculates the heating, cooling, and domestic hot water (DHW) energy demand results for each building or area under study.

3.1. Input data block

The input data block is divided in two main sections: (1) Data Source, which describes the input data required for the DMM; and (2) Data Pre-processing, in which adaptation, cleaning, and organisation of the existing data are performed.

3.1.1. Data sources

The input data required for the DMM are based on different information sources: information related to cartography and cadastral data, Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) information, and air temperature data.

Datasets containing the cartographic and cadastral information, which are needed to start the process described in Fig. 1, should be available as open data or provided by the municipality. The accuracy of the results provided by the DMM depends on the availability of data and its level of detail and veracity. This means that data sources providing information at the parcel level collected five years ago will produce results that are less reliable than data sources in which the information is defined at the building level and has been recently updated. Additionally, the access to information produced by governments used to be restricted. However, governments have updated this information in the last years and provide it as open data to generate economic and civic value light detection and ranging [25]. The OpenStreetMap (OSM) is an alternative for cartographic data if the municipality does not have the relevant information. The OSM is a free and editable map of the whole world that is being built by volunteers from scratch and released with an open-content license [26].

Another required data source includes LiDAR data: a system that generates a point cloud of the ground by means of an airborne laser scanner. A Digital Surface Model (DSM) and Digital Terrain Model (DTM) can be derived from the LiDAR data. The DSM and DTM are 3D representations of the topography, stored as a matrix of points with heights. The DSM represents the elevation of natural and built features on the Earth's surface, while the DTM represents the elevation of the Earth's surface. The LiDAR data are increasingly available, in particular for urban areas. These data should also be available for the municipality.

Finally, the required heating degree-hour (HDH) and cooling degree-hour (CDH) data are retrieved from the air temperature data generated by the National Observatory of Athens (NOA) now-casting service [27]. This service has been operational since 2015 and exploits thermal satellite data from SEVIRI [28] and information from the Global Forecasting System to generate five-min 1 km × 1 km air temperature (TA) maps. The processing scheme of NOA is based on several in-house algorithms [27] and on the physical retrieval algorithm (SPHR-PGE13 algorithm) of the Satellite Ap-

Fig. 1. Scheme and workflow of the calculation process of the District Mapping Module, where two main blocks are defined: Input Data and District Energy Assessment.

plication Facility for Nowcasting Weather Conditions software [29]. The HDH and CDH are estimated using Eqs. (1) and (2), respectively, where j is the day-of-year; i is the hour-of-day; and $T_{b,H}$ and $T_{b,C}$ are the base temperatures of Eqs. (1) and (2), respectively (only positive values are considered).

$$HDH_{i,j} = (T_{b,H} - TA_{i,j})_{((T_{b,H} - TA_{i,j}) > 0)} \quad (1)$$

$$CDH_{i,j} = (TA_{i,j} - T_{b,C})_{((TA_{i,j} - T_{b,C}) > 0)} \quad (2)$$

3.1.2. Data pre-processing

In general, different data sources have to be combined to include all necessary information in a single file. If the cadastral data are obsolete, outdated, or do not exist, the cadastral data can alternatively be obtained from the OSM. Although the semantic information is usually poor, the geometrical information tends to be updated and is available at the building scale (and not at parcel level). Irrespective of the data source, it is necessary to delete all irrelevant information to simplify and focus on required data. Therefore, the information is adapted, cleaned, and organised in an initial data pre-processing step. Common problems associated with the pre-processing of multiple layers are:

- The information is not included in a unique layer; therefore, multiple layers (such as plots and buildings) need to be mixed.
- Information that comes from different sources does not have a shared identifier, which means that different geological processes must be performed to link or associate the data. Also, the coordinate reference systems may be different.
- There are layers in which polygons represent different building parts with different heights. These polygons need to be removed or mixed into a unique building.
- There is no agreement on the representation of some of the properties of the building such as the building use.
- Sometimes, the geometry of the buildings is too complex and requires simplification (e.g. a polygon representing a footprint of a building with more than 100 vertices).
- The semantic information is not complete for all buildings and rows with no data need to be discarded to avoid errors.
- Inconsistencies in the data, such as incorrect building usage or number of floors, lead to undesired results.

For that purpose, different layers are combined using geospatial processes such as intersection or unions. Also, unnecessary geometries and parameters are deleted.

The DSM and DTM are derived from LiDAR data; they usually are huge files, which may require some pre-processing. The DSM and DTM data can be stored in multiple formats. In our case, the ASC II Grid format was used. To improve the performance of the data, DSM and DTM data should be limited to the area of the study.

As output of this pre-processing step, a shape file with a unique geometry needs to be created for each building including the following mandatory parameters (see Table 1): building ID, geometry of the building, building footprint area, year of construction, use, and building height. However, the height of the building can be directly defined as an input of the cadastral data or calculated using the provided LiDAR data. The LiDAR data can be processed and combined with the cadastral information during the processing of the DMM data (see Section 3.2.1), providing the height of each building. Additional non-mandatory parameters, such as the gross floor area, number of floors, or roof area, can also be used as input; however, in case they are not, they will be estimated during data processing.

3.2. District energy assessment block

The District Energy Assessment (DEA) is divided into four main sections: (1) data processing, where the input data block is processed to obtain new semantic and geometric information relevant for the energy assessment; (2) inference rules, which define several functions linking the outputs of the data processing with the algorithm inputs and DEA database; (3) internal energy assessment algorithm, which is used to assess the energy demand of each building; and (4) outputs.

3.2.1. Data processing

The purpose of the data processing section is to automatically process the outputs of the input data block to obtain new semantic and geometric information to be used in the inference rule and internal algorithm sections.

The initial step of the data processing focuses on the mapping of the information provided by the pre-processed shape file and

Table 1

Mandatory and optional input data of the DMM plugin and the information sources of each input.

Parameter	Mandatory or optional	Source
Building ID	Mandatory	SHP of the District
Building Geometry	Mandatory	SHP of the District
Footprint area	Mandatory	SHP of the District
Height	Mandatory	SHP of the District or LiDAR
Hourly outside air temperature	Mandatory	NOAs webserver
Year of construction	Mandatory	SHP of the District
Building Use	Mandatory	SHP of the District
Gross floor area	Optional	SHP of the District
Number of floors	Optional	SHP of the District
Roof area	Optional	SHP of the District

Table 2

Output parameters of the data-process section of the DMM, their format and the calculation method of each of these output parameters.

Parameter	Format	Calculation method
Building ID	Text	Input
Centroid of the building	Coordinate	Calculated
Country	Text	Input
Year of construction	Number	Input
Building Use	Text	Input + mapping
Number of floors	Number	Input (shape) or if not given it is estimated
Height	Number	Input (shape) or calculated from LiDAR data
Footprint area	Number (m ²)	Input
Gross floor area	Number (m ²)	Input (shape) or if not given it is estimated
Net heated area	Number (m ²)	Estimated
Roof area	Number (m ²)	Input (shape) or if not given it is estimated
External façade area	Number (m ²)	Estimated
Heated volume	Number (m ³)	Estimated
Centroid of the study	Coordinate	Calculated

data required by the DEA. To define the 'building use' parameter, nine different uses have been defined in the DEA: residential, office, education, hospital, commerce, hotel, public administration, restaurant, and sport centres. This step links the uses defined in the cadastral map of the municipality with the uses defined by the DEA. When the mapping step ends, the data processing section processes the shape file and LiDAR data (if available) to obtain the parameters defined in Table 2.

The parameters listed in Table 2 are described in detail below, specifying their source and calculation process:

Building ID: A unique text assigned to a building to differentiate it from the others.

Centroid of the building: The centroid is calculated by obtaining the arithmetic mean position of all points of the building footprint polygon.

Country: The country in which the study area is located is a very important parameter due to its influence on the calculations. Some of the parameters specified in the DEA, such as the U value, air renovations, or solar gains, are defined for each of the countries in the EU. This will be explained in more detail in Section 3.2.2.

Year of construction: This value defines the construction year of each building or the year when this building is registered in the cadastre. Most of the existing buildings have been refurbished during the last decades. However, information about these renovation activities in the cadastre is usually very limited. This means that the cadastre does not contain specific information and normally is limited to a general description such as installation of an elevator, change of the boiler, and improvement of the facade. This methodology therefore proposes to use the initial construction year for all buildings based on the limitation of the cadastral information regarding the thermal characteristics of the refurbished building.

Use: Residential buildings account for 76% of the total stock in Europe. Single family houses and apartment blocks account for 64% and 36% of the residential buildings, respectively. On the other

hand, non-residential buildings account for 24% of the total stock in Europe [11]. Based on the structure of the current European building stock, this methodology defines nine different building uses, that is, two residential (single family house and apartment blocks) and 7 non-residential or tertiary uses (office – public administration, health care, commerce, education, hotel, restaurant and sport centre).

Number of floors: When the number of floors (NF) is not provided by the cadastre, it is calculated by dividing the building height by the floor-to-floor (FTF) height. The value of the FTF height varies depending on the use of each building. When the height of the building and number of floors are defined in the cadastre, this parameter does not have any influence on the calculations. The assumption of an average height of 3 m per storey might be too simple and lead to errors. Therefore, there are several references [30,31] or tools, such as the Height Calculator developed by the Council on Tall Buildings Urban Habitat [32], which allow a better definition of the FTF height depending on the use of the building.

Height: The building height can be specified in the cadastre. It can be obtained from the LiDAR files or calculated by multiplying the NF by the FTF height. To obtain the building height using LiDAR, a list with all points that are within each building is created for the DSM and DTM. To discard atypical values (very low or very high values), a cleaning process is performed prior to calculating the percentile. Therefore, the 5th and 95th percentiles are calculated and then a new list is created including the values between both percentiles. Finally, the desired percentile is calculated with the new list. In this method, the 90th percentile was calculated. For this purpose, all heights that are within the building were ordered by increasing height. Then, the following equation was used: $\text{perc90Index} = \text{listSize} \times 90/100$. The 90th percentile will be the value of the list that is in the position of the index (perc90Index).

Table 3
Inference rules between the data process outputs and DEA database.

	Age range	Schedules	Internal gains	WWR	U-value	Ventilation losses	Solar gains	DHW demand
Country					X	X	X	
Year of construction	X				X	X		
Use		X	X	X	X		X	X

Gross floor area: According to DIN 277-1:2016-01 [33], the gross floor area (GFA) of a building is the total usable surface area of all floor plan levels and their constructive enclosure (without the deduction of corridors, stairways, closets, thickness of interior walls, columns, or other features). It is therefore measured according to the external dimensions of a building. Based on this methodology, the GFA value can be obtained by multiplying the footprint area with the number of floors.

Net heated area: The net heated area (NHA) is the heated and/or air-conditioned floor area, which does not consider circulation areas or technical spaces [33, 34]. The relation between the GFA and NHA is directly related to the use of each building and is defined by the Gross to Heated Ratio (GHR) [35–38]. Based on this methodology, the NHA is obtained by dividing the GFA by the GHR.

Roof area: If this value is not available in case a flat roof has been considered for all buildings, the value of the footprint area is used as roof area. However, there are different approaches to more precisely calculate the roof area by considering its slope [39].

External facade area: First, each envelope surface is analysed to check if it is an external or an adjoining wall. An envelope surface is considered to be an adjoining wall in case both the surface and adjacent surfaces follow the same direction.

Heated volume: The heated volume (HV) is the amount of volume that is going to be heated, cooled, and/or ventilated. This value is calculated (see Eq. (3)) by considering the NHA, height of the building, NF of each building, and thickness of the internal slabs (TIS).

$$HV_k = NHA_k / NF_k \times (Height_k - (NF_k \times TIS_k)) \quad (3)$$

Centroid of the area under study: The centroid of every building is calculated using geometric information. The centroid of the area under study is then calculated as the average point of all centroids.

3.2.2. Inference rules and DEA database

After data processing, each building is characterised (see Section 3.2.1.) However, to carry out the energy demand assessment, this information is not sufficient and more specific data are required. Therefore, a set of inference rules has been defined to automatise the process, linking the outputs of the data processing with the information obtained from several European databases and other information sources (see Table 3). An inference rule is a logical form consisting of a function, which uses the premises, analyses their syntax, and returns a conclusion. This way, the DEA database including all required information is developed based on existing sources of information.

Age range: To organise the data of the internal DEA database based on the classification defined by the European Observatory [40], the year of construction of each building is classified into seven ranks: Pre-1945, 1945–1969, 1970–1979, 1980–1989, 1990–1999, 2000–2010, and Post-2010. This ranking will simplify the definition of the parameters such as the U-value or number of air changes per hour.

Schedules: The occupancy pattern of a building considerably varies depending on its use and the behaviour of its occupants. However, it is very difficult to define generic patterns for each use because of the large differences that may exist, especially in the case of residential buildings [41]. The DEA has implemented a total of 40 usage patterns, that is, heating, cooling, occupancy, lighting,

and equipment for each of the eight uses (the schedule is the same for both residential uses). Only two values are used in the case of heating and cooling, that is, 1 and 0, representing the on/off states, respectively. However, these values can take different fractions for occupancy, lighting, and equipment. Due to the difficulty in generating a generic standard for residential buildings, for example, for hotels and hospitals, the schedule is considered to be the same for all days of the week, whereas working days and weekends are considered for the rest of the uses. The established heating and cooling periods are winter and summer, respectively. Winter is often defined by meteorologists to be the three calendar months with the lowest average temperatures: December, January, and February (in the Northern Hemisphere). However, the winter and summer periods of each country or region can vary according to the climatic data. Therefore, this methodology proposes to adapt these periods to each case study.

Internal gains: The internal gains are different depending on the use of the building because of the associated occupation pattern and equipment. The required lighting and patterns of use are different. To assess the internal gains of each building, several parameters have been defined in this methodology. The radiant and convective fractions are based on the study of Saelen et al. [42]. The internal occupancy gains are assessed considering the occupancy level per unit of area of the building (density) and the energy that a person releases per unit of time (metabolic rate). To obtain these values for each building use and information about appliances and equipment gains, this methodology is based on the information provided by the simulation tool Design Builder® [13]. Finally, considering that the lighting requirements differ depending on the use of each building, the installed lighting power density is established based on American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) association [43].

Window-to-wall ratio (WWR): Based on several scientific studies, this methodology suggests a window-to-wall ratio (%) for each of the nine building uses defined previously: residential single family house, 13% [44]; residential apartment blocks, 27% [45]; office–public administration, 50% [46]; health care, 23% [46]; commerce, 20% [47]; education, 28% [15]; hotel, 17% [48]; restaurants, 30% (study assumption); and sport centre, 20% (study assumption). However, according to the availability of information, these ratios should be adapted for each case study.

U-value: The insulation of a building varies depending on its location, typology, construction period, or element to be evaluated and is determined by the U-value of the elements that compose the envelope. The U-value, that is, the heat transfer coefficient or thermal transmittance, measures the heat loss through an element. To generate a complete, reliable, and rigorous internal database, the search for the U-values has been conducted using databases generated in different research projects in this methodology [8,40,49]. The classification of the data was performed according to the country in the European Union, construction period of the buildings (classified into seven ranks: Pre-1945, 1945–1969, 1970–1979, 1980–1989, 1990–1999, 2000–2010, Post-2010), building use (two main groups: residential and service), and envelope element (roof, façade and window).

Ventilation losses: The ventilation losses are the product of the indoor–outdoor temperature difference, building heated volume,

hourly air exchange, specific heat capacity of air, and remaining fraction after considering the heat recovery. The flow of heat loss through ventilation can be expressed with Eq. (4) [50]. Based on the work by Kemna and Acedo [38], this methodology defines the value of the air changes (including infiltrations and intentional ventilation through open windows and/or mechanical ventilation) per hour according to the country in which the assessed area is located and construction period of the building to be evaluated. The heated volume of each building is obtained through data processing (see Section 3.2.1.).

$$\text{Ventilation heat loss}_{i,j} = 0.33 \cdot N_k \cdot HV_k \cdot \Delta T_{i,j} \quad (4)$$

Solar gains: The solar gains are defined as the useful thermal energy that reaches the interior of the buildings through the windows (direct solar gains). The influence of solar heat gains results from the local solar radiation, orientation of the facades, and position and geometry of the building (windows) and surroundings. Although the solar gains should be calculated according to EN 13790 [51], several building energy performance standards consider solar gains to be default values (17–18 kWh/m² heated floor area) or integrate a ‘correction solar gain’ factor by increasing the indoor temperature by 1.2 °C [38]. However, to integrate this parameter in the DEA with enough accuracy instead of using simplified methods, representative dynamic simulations have been carried out using Design Builder® based on which hourly solar gains per window area (W/m²) are obtained. This methodology has been used for 56 simulations, two (residential and office building uses) for each EU country. Based on these results, the DEA integrates the solar gains in the assessment algorithm.

Domestic hot water demand: Unlike the heating and cooling demand, the domestic hot water (DHW) demand is independent of constructive characteristics of buildings and therefore of their age; it is only affected by the building use. Therefore, the DHW demand for each building use is defined based on the domestic water heating design manual developed by American Society of Plumbing Engineers (ASPE) [52].

3.2.3. Internal energy assessment algorithm

The main objective of the internal energy assessment algorithm of the DEA is to assess the useful thermal energy demand of each building in terms of heating, cooling, and DHW. To simplify the assessment, static equations following the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive [12] are used to determine the energy demand (see Eqs. (5)(7)). The static calculation is preferable for the early stage of an assessment by the municipality. Full dynamic modelling with accurate results will be used for advanced design stages that require a large amount of input data and technical partners.

The complexity of the assessment and accuracy of the results vary in a static calculation depending on the parameters that are considered and the time resolution of the assessment. On one hand, the approach defined in this study considers most of the parameters, except for thermal inertia, that are analysed by existing dynamic simulation tools such as Design Builder®. On the other hand, usually static approaches are used at a coarser time resolution (typically yearly or monthly values) because they smooth out typical dynamic phenomena that characterise the thermal behaviour of a building per day (thermal inertia, for example). However, this type of yearly or monthly time resolution makes it difficult to consider relevant parameters, such as the influence of different schedules (heating, cooling, occupation, and internal gains), which allow the assessment and analysis of the results of each building use in a different way and with more detailed information. This differentiation might be relevant to end users, such as municipalities, because they have the possibility to focus their effort on a specific building typology in each study area or work on control systems. In addition, yearly or monthly time resolutions do

not consider the hourly outdoor air temperature in their calculation process. Therefore, they are not useful to assess the value of the peak power demand or define the size of active strategies such as district heating. Therefore, based on the need to distinguish the energy demand for each building use and to provide the peak demand for the PlanHeat tool, this methodology uses static hourly calculations.

The hourly heating demand of each building is determined by multiplying the number of heating degree hours with the particular location, heat transfer coefficient of the envelope areas, and heating schedule for each hour. The annual demand is the sum of the hourly heating demands (see Eq. (5)). The HDH value is provided by the input data block (see Section 3.1.1.). Losses through the ground are neglected but might have an impact on the overall heating demand. Different internal gains related to occupancy, lighting, appliances, and solar gains are considered (see Section 3.2.2.). Finally, ventilation losses (calculated considering different base temperatures for heating or cooling) are assumed based on the proposal defined in Section 3.2.2. If a mechanical ventilation system with heat recovery is installed, the ventilation losses are reduced by the heat recovery system efficiency. The annual cooling demand of each building is determined using Eq. (6), that is, by replacing HDH with CDH. Finally, the annual DHW demand is determined by multiplying the annual DHW demand per square meter with the net heated area of the building, and normalised usage factor of the DHW (see Eq. (7)).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{AHD}_k = \sum_{i,j=1}^{8760} & \left(\text{HDH}_{i,j} \times A_k \times U_k - \text{Gains}_{i,j} \right. \\ & \left. + \text{hventilation losses}_{i,j} \times (1 - n_{HR}) \right) \cdot \text{heating schedule}_{i,j} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ACD}_k = \sum_{i,j=1}^{8760} & \left(\text{CDH}_{i,j} \times A_k \times U_k + \text{Gains}_{i,j} \right. \\ & \left. + \text{cventilation losses}_{i,j} \times (1 - n_{HR}) \right) \cdot \text{cooling schedule}_{i,j} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{DHW}D_k = \sum_{i,j=1}^{8760} & \text{DHW demand}_k \times \text{NHA}_k \\ & \times \frac{\text{Hourly usage factor}_{\text{DHW}_{i,j}}}{\sum_{i,j=1}^{8760} \text{Hourly usage factor}_{\text{DHW}_{i,j}}} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

3.2.4. Output data

Based on Eqs. (5)–(7), the DEA will automatically obtain different types of results from the selected study area. The assessment scale of this methodology makes it possible to analyse the obtained results per building or district.

At the building scale, this method generates georeferenced, generic, and energy information for each building of the area under study (see Table 4).

This method generates two different results for the district or study area levels. The first output provides annual heating, cooling, and DHW energy demand data classified according to the age range and building use. The second output provides hourly heating, cooling, and DHW energy demand data for the whole study area.

4. Description of the case study

The methodology described in Section 3 has been validated based on the application to the historical district of Antwerp. It

Table 4
Outputs of the District Energy Assessment block at building level.

Parameter	Unit	Parameter	Unit
Project generic data			
Project ID	Name	Study area name	Name
Country	Name		
Building generic data			
Building ID		Centroid of the building	Coordinates
Use	Name	Footprint area	m ²
Height	Number	Number of floors	Number
Net heated area	m ²	External opaque facade area	m ²
Roof area	m ²	Window area	m ²
Heated volume	m ³	Age range	Number
Building energy data			
Annual heating demand	kWh/year	Annual heating demand per square meter	kWh/(m ² year)
Annual cooling demand	kWh/year	Annual cooling demand per square meter	kWh/(m ² year)
Annual DHW demand	kWh/year	Annual DHW demand per square meter	kWh/(m ² year)
Peak heating demand	kW	Peak cooling demand	kW
Peak DHW demand	kW		

Table 5
Comparison between the column headers of the case study of Antwerp with the DEA method.

Column Header of the Antwerp Municipality input	Column Header of the DEA
OBJECTID_1	Building ID
BEBOUWDE_O	Footprint area
NH_P99	Height
BOUWJAAR_M	Year of construction
PERCEEL_GE	Building Use
VERDIEPEN	Number of floors

allows the analysis of a group of buildings and evaluation of their energy performance based on cadastral data. Antwerp is a Flemish city in Belgium. It is the capital of the Antwerp Province in the community of Flanders. With a population of 517,042 people, it is the most populous city in Belgium. Its metropolitan area accommodates approximately 1,200,000 people, which puts it into second place behind Brussels. The historical city area covers 398,276 m² and includes approximately 1676 buildings. It is relevant to highlight that 73% of the buildings in this district were built before 1945 and only 6.9% were built or refurbished after 1990. Due to the commercial use of most of the basement floors and the location of several office and public administration buildings, 48% of the GFA has tertiary use.

According to the Köppen climate classification [53], the climate of Antwerp is oceanic climate, that is, a climate with cool summers and cool (but not cold) winters and with a relatively narrow annual temperature range. The average annual temperature is 10.6 °C. In summer, the daily average temperature is below 17.8 °C. Therefore, cooling systems are generally unnecessary, especially if measures such as solar shading or night cooling are implemented. Based on the information provided by NOA's module, the annual heating and cooling degree values are 2398 and 0 at a base temperature of 21 °C (heating) and 25 °C (cooling), respectively. The heating and cooling periods established for this case study are 1 November to 31 March and 1 April to 31 October, respectively.

4.1. Input data

In the case of Antwerp, the municipality provided the cadastral information at two levels: parcels and building. The first one contains the geometry and semantic information of the whole parcel such as year of construction, main use, and number of floors. The second one provides a more detailed geometry, which is closer to the real geometry of the building but includes few semantic information. It is therefore necessary to pre-processing the cadastral information to obtain a unique input shape file at the building level

by selecting the most realistic and detailed geometry, performing data cleaning, and combining the semantic information of the two original files.

The pre-processing is carried out with a desktop GIS software (QGIS) in which several geological processes can be performed. The striped polygon represents the parcel (which holds most of the semantic information) and the dotted polygons are the buildings (which have the most detailed geometry) within that parcel. A spatial overlay has been performed between parcel and building layers to combine their semantic information.

4.2. Assessment of the case study

After the pre-processing step, the assessment of the study area is started. Because of the information source and language of the input file, a mapping process is needed to connect the column headers of the shape file with parameters of the DEA (see Table 5) and uses defined by the municipality of Antwerp with building uses of the DEA (see Table 6).

Because the cadastral information provides data related to the height and number of floors of each building, the FTF value is automatically obtained during the data processing. On the other hand, to assess the NHA, this case study considers the GHR values defined in Table 6. Finally, anTIS of 0.3 m is used.

Table 6 shows that three of the uses obtained from the cadastral data do not have an equivalent in the proposed method; the industry and religious facilities are out of the scope. In the case of unknown use, it is not possible to establish any type of pattern for the inference rules (i.e. to consider any predefined internal gains or to determine the percentage of glazing of the building). Thus, buildings with any of the three above-mentioned uses have been excluded from the analysis of the district, corresponding to a total of 52 buildings. Table 7 lists more information about the buildings of this case study such as the areas for different buildings, rates for their WWRs, and U-values.

Table 6

Comparison between the building uses of the case study of Antwerp with the DEA method; and the Gross to Heated ratio (GHR) value per each building use defined by the DEA.

Use defined by the Antwerp municipality	Use defined by the DEA	GHR value[38]
House	Residential, single family house	1.57
Residential apartment	Residential, apartment block	1.57
Residential/commercial apartment	Residential, apartment block	1.57
Commercial apartment	Commerce	1.27
Company	Office-Public administration	1.65
Office	Office-Public administration	1.65
Government	Office-Public administration	1.65
Horeca (hotel, restaurant, cafe)	Hotel	1.60
Culture/sport facility	Sport centre	1.31
Health/social facility	Hospital	2.00
Education facility	Education	1.53
Industry	None (out of the scope)	–
Religious facility	None (out of the scope)	–
Unknown	None	–

Table 7

Gross floor area (GFA), window to wall ratio (WWR), air change per hour (ACH) and U-values information of the buildings of this case study according to their age ranges.

	Pre-1945	1945–69	1970–79	1980–89	1990–99	2000–10	Post-2010	WWR
Gross floor area (m²) of different building uses: residential single-family house (RSF), residential apartment blocks (RAB), office - public administration (OF), health care (HC), commerce (CO), education (ED), hotel (HO), restaurant (RE), sport centre (SC) and not evaluated (NE)								
RSF	31,742	2657	1926	3285	337	518	0	13%
RAB	120,139	34,902	17,231	33,053	59,596	26,965	14,780	27%
OF	197,057	52,620	6282	7906	1202	103	0	50%
ED	10,209	0	0	14,393	0	0	0	28%
HC	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23%
CO	9877	1724	1663	1872	4575	4094	0	20%
HO	4567	2784	329	0	0	0	0	17%
SC	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20%
RE	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	30%
NE	27,883	33,643	0	23	0	0	0	–
Air change per hour								
District	1.2	1.2	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.7	0.7	–
U values (W/m²) of Residential (R) and non-residential (NR) buildings								
R_roof	2.3	2.3	2.3	1.1	0.9	0.6	0.6	–
R_wall	1.9	1.9	1.7	1.6	1.2	0.8	0.8	–
R_window	4.5	4.5	3.9	3.8	3.8	2.5	2.5	–
NR_roof	2	2	2.2	1.2	0.9	0.7	0.7	–
NR_wall	1.9	1.8	1.8	1.7	1.3	0.8	0.8	–
NR_window	4.5	4.6	4.2	3.8	3.7	2.3	2.3	–

Table 8

Example of the data-process outputs for one of the buildings of the area under study: Building ID 5321306.

Project generic data					
Project ID	Country	Antwerp project	Belgium	Study area name	Historical City
Building generic data					
Building ID	5321306	Centroid building	51.223, 4.403	Use	Residential, apartment block
Age range	Pre 1945	Number of floors	5	Gross floor area (m ²)	235
Height (m)	15.6	Roof area (m ²)	47	Heated volume (m ³)	419.4
Footprint area (m ²)	47				
Net heated area (m ²)	148.7				
External Facade area (m ²)	74.3				

The result of the data processing for the buildings within the study area is a CSV file including the parameters previously defined in Section 3.2.1. (see Table 8).

After generating this CSV file for the historical city of Antwerp, the characteristics are linked to the previously defined inference rules (see Section 3.2.2.) to calculate the new inputs needed for the internal energy assessment algorithm (see Table 9). The specific schedule information is based on the assumptions defined in Section 3.2.2. Finally, hourly heating and cooling degree values are obtained based on the information provided by NOAs service.

After defining and obtaining all necessary parameters, the internal energy assessment algorithm starts the assessment of the study area. As an example, this section describes the calculation

process of the proposed methodology for a specific day (9 January) and specific hour (12:00 (UTC + 2)) for the selected building (Building ID 5321306). The algorithm will carry out the same calculation hourly, allowing the assessment of the heating, cooling, and DHW for each hour of the year and each building of the district. The first section of Eqs. (5) and (6) quantify the thermal conductivity losses (TCL) of the building, which are directly related to the surface and thermal transmittance parameters of the facade, roof, and windows (see equation below).

$$TCL_{i,j} (kw) = \frac{[(A_f \times U_f) + (A_r \times U_r) + (A_w \times U_w)] \times HDH_{i,j}}{1000} \quad (8)$$

Table 9

Outputs related to the building 5321306 of the case study obtained after the application of the inference rules and the DEA database.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
External opaque façade area (m ²)	54.2	Glazing area (m ²)	20.1
U-value, roof (W/(m ² K))	2.3	U-value, facade (W/m ² K)	1.9
U-value, window (W/(m ² K))	4.5	Internal gains, occupancy (W/m ²)	1.7
Internal gains, equipment (W/m ²)	1.3	Internal gains, lighting (W/m ²)	3.2
Air change per hour	1.2	DHW demand (kWh/m ²)	13.9

Table 10

Useful heating (Heat), cooling (cool) and Domestic hot water (DHW) energy demand of the Antwerp Historic City according the building age range and the use of the buildings.

Building age range	Use	Energy demand					
		Total (Kwh/year)			Per square meter (kWh/(m ² year))		
		Heating	Cooling	DHW	Heating	Cooling	DHW
Pre-1945	Residential	22,191,536	1,131,621	2,111,140	146.11	7.45	13.90
	Tertiary	24,669,391	3,488,349	4,143,064	111.02	15.70	18.64
1945–1969	Residential	4,315,716	211,321	522,071	114.90	5.63	13.90
	Tertiary	3,619,776	767,285	760,440	62.49	13.25	13.13
1970–1979	Residential	1,839,785	178,617	266,279	96.04	9.32	13.90
	Tertiary	843,428	104,011	91,670	101.95	12.57	11.08
1980–1989	Residential	4,118,012	567,868	505,096	113.33	15.63	13.90
	Tertiary	1,526,931	473,667	1,174,039	63.17	19.60	48.57
1990–1999	Residential	3,884,781	653,668	833,074	64.82	10.91	13.90
	Tertiary	838,325	82,730	18,485	145.12	14.32	3.20
2000–2010	Residential	1,088,080	351,202	382,017	39.59	12.78	13.90
	Tertiary	907,239	79,557	13,428	216.20	18.96	3.20
Post-2010	Residential	568,223	170,072	205,446	38.44	11.51	13.90
	Tertiary	–	–	–	–	–	–
Total		70,411,222	8,259,965	11,026,251			

$$\begin{aligned}
 TCL_{12:00, 09th Jan} &= \frac{(54.2 \times 1.9) + (47 \times 2.3) + (20.1 \times 4.5)}{1000} \times 14.2 \\
 &= 4.3 \text{ kW}
 \end{aligned}$$

The second section of Eqs. (5) and (6) quantifies the internal gains (IG) of the building, which are directly related to the different types of gains, convective fraction, and schedule (see equation below).

$$\begin{aligned}
 IG_{i,j} \text{ (kw)} &= \frac{[(G_o \times CF_o \times S_{o,i,j}) + (G_e \times CF_e \times S_{e,i,j}) + (G_l \times CF_l \times S_{l,i,j}) + (G_{S_{i,j}})] \times NHA_k}{1000} \quad (9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 IG_{12:00, 09th Jan} &= \frac{[(3.5 \times 0.5 \times 0.2) + (4.4 \times 0.3 \times 0.3) + (6.4 \times 0.5 \times 0.3) + (18.3)] \times 148.7}{1000} \\
 &= 2.9 \text{ kW}
 \end{aligned}$$

Finally, the third section of Eqs. (5) and (6) quantifies the ventilation losses (VL) of the building, which are directly related to Eqs. (3) and (4).

$$VL_{heating_{12:00, 09th Jan}} = \frac{0.33 \times 1.2 \times 419.4 \times 14.2}{1000} = 2.4 \text{ kW}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 VL_{cooling_{12:00, 09th Jan}} &= \frac{0.33 \times 1.2 \times 419.4 \times (-18.2)}{1000} \\
 &= -3.1 \text{ kW}
 \end{aligned}$$

Eqs. (10) and (11) show how the DEA obtains the heating energy demand (HHD) and cooling energy demand (HCD) values for this specific hour.

$$HHD_{12:00, 09th Jan} = (4.3 - 2.9 + 2.4) \times 1 = 3.8 \text{ kW} \quad (10)$$

$$HCD_{12:00, 09th Jan} = (0 + 2.9 + (-3.1)) \times 0 = 0 \text{ kW} \quad (11)$$

Finally, a DWH energy demand of 0.25 kW is obtained at 12:00 (UTC + 2) on 9 January based on Eq. (7).

4.3. Results of the analysis

This section explains the results obtained using the DMM method for the study area. One of the main results is shown in Fig. 2, a shape file that highlights one of the results at the building level, that is, the annual heating demand per square meter geo-referenced for each building. Note that this shape file contains all outputs at the building level (described in Section 3.2.4.).

Fig. 2 can be used to detect the areas with the highest energy demand in the historical district of Antwerp and to relate these demands to the type of building according to its use, age range, or other parameter associated with each building. For example, the treatment of the output shape file shows that the heating and DHW energy demand of more than 23.5% of the buildings and more than 14.56% of the NHA is greater than 166 kWh/m², which reflects the average heating and DHW energy demand for existing buildings of Belgium [54]. This value highlights the inefficient energy performance and need to improve all these buildings. In addition to the implementation of passive strategies and considering the heritage of the district, high efficient active systems and renewable energy should also be considered to improve the sustainability of the energy supply system of the historical centre of Antwerp.

In addition to this individualised information per building, Table 10 shows the aggregate energy values of the study area. The results listed in Table 10 show that 78.5% of the thermal energy demand of this district is related to the heating demand (70,411 MWh/year), 12.3% to the DHW demand (11,026 MWh/year), and 9.2% to the cooling demand (8259 MWh/year) based on aspects such as the

Fig. 2. Visualisation of the annual heating energy demand per square meter (kwh/m^2) of the case study by QGIS.

Fig. 3. Hourly heating and Domestic hot water (DHW) energy demand of the Historic District of Antwerp during the whole year (8760 h).

Antwerp climate or the thermal performance of the old building envelope of the historical district.

Residential buildings represent 54% of the district's total heating demand. Among these residential buildings, pre-1945 account for the largest portion of the total heating demand, that is, 31.5%. Tertiary buildings account for 60.5% of the district's total cooling demand. In this case, pre-1945 tertiary buildings are responsible for 42.2% of the district's total cooling demand. Finally, tertiary buildings built before 1945 reflect 37.6% of the district's total DHW demand.

Finally, the hourly energy demand results allow the evaluation of different thermal needs during sequential seasons of the year (Fig. 3). The analysis of the district's total hourly demand, among other options, allows the evaluation of the potential and size of strategies such as district heating. For example, in this case study, the installation of a district heating system with a biomass boiler of 5 GW would facilitate the supply of the thermal heating and DHW for the entire district for 6080 h, that is, 69% of the year. However, if the district heating system would only be responsible for the DHW demand, the heating system would be able to supply the entire district's demand throughout the year. If a boiler with a power of 10 GW was installed, this system would generate enough thermal energy to supply the demand for 6294 h (72%). Finally, if

the power would be increased to a 20 GW boiler, the system would generate power for 7219h (82%).

5. Validation

This section will focus on the analysis of the reliability and thoroughness of the results obtained using the DMM method defined in this article. Two different validations have been carried out, which are directly related to the case study of the historical city of Antwerp. The first one aims to compare the results of the methodology with the results of an existing energy simulation tool. The second validation focuses on the comparison of the results of the DMM method with the real natural gas consumption of a sector of the historical district.

5.1. Comparison with the dynamic simulation tool

This first validation aims to evaluate the variation between the results of the energy demand obtained using this methodology and those from an existing dynamic energy simulation tool. Energyplus [14], a widely recognised energy simulation tool, and the International Weather for Energy Calculation (climatic files) were used for

Fig. 4. Design Builder models of four representative buildings of the Historic district of Antwerp. Each model is defined by the cadastral information of Antwerp and the acronym defined by this article.

Table 11

Percentage of number of buildings of the most representative buildings of the case study according to its use (residential single-family house (RSF), residential apartment blocks (RAB), office - public administration (OF)), age range and number of adiabatic walls.

Use	Age range	Percentage of number of buildings (%)	Acronym
RSF	<1945	12.3	RSF.1
RAB	<1945	20.7	RAB.1
	1945–69	3.7	RAB.2
	1980–89	4.7	RAB.3
	1990–99	3.1	RAB.4
OF	<1945	36.5	OF.1
	1945–69	4.1	OF.2

this validation [55]. The building models were developed using the Design Builder® interface (Table 10).

To choose the most representative buildings of this district, a clustering analysis was performed in this study. This clustering has been carried out based on three main parameters for each building: use, age range, and number of external facades in contact with another heated area (adjoining walls). In total, 1621 buildings were analysed in this case study. Table 11 shows the seven main typologies, which represent 85% of all buildings in the historical district of Antwerp.

The analysis of the number of floors of the different building typologies in the case study shows that most of the residential family houses have two floors, residential apartment blocks have four floors, and offices have three floors. The analysis of the building geometry of the district shows that most of the buildings have between two and three adjoining walls. Therefore, two buildings were modelled for each of the representative building typologies in Design Builder®, one with two (2AD) and the other one with three (3AD) adjoining walls such that a total of 14 scenarios were created.

Fig. 4 shows the Design Builder models of four representative buildings, where the grey block represents the assessed building and the red blocks define the adiabatic wall. Each building in Fig. 4 is described by two parameters: the identification (ID) defined by the cadastral information of Antwerp (for example 3737081) and the acronym defined in this article (RSF.1.2AD). Finally, the parameters, such as the occupancy rate, schedules, internal gains, U-values, window-to-wall ratio, and air changes, are based on the information defined by the DEA.

Fig. 5 shows the difference (in percentage) between the results obtained for each representative building from both methodologies, that is, the DMM and Design Builder. In conjunction with the annual energy demand for heating (AHD), cooling (ACD) and DHW (DHW), this analysis also compares the results for the main thermal parameters that influence the energy calculation, that is, TCL, IG, solar gains (GS), and VL.

The results show that the difference in the calculation of the heating demand, refrigeration, and DHW ranges between 3% and 11%, 2% and 11%, and 8% and 10%, respectively. Four main parameters influence the calculation of the two initial points (heating and cooling demands). The first parameter is the TCL. The results of this case study show that due to factors, such as the influence of the thermal inertia of the walls, considered by the DB or the difference between the assessment algorithms considered by each methodology, the percentage difference of the TCL between both methodologies varies between 1% up to 12%. However, considering that the main information source of the DMM method is the municipal cadastre, it is very difficult to obtain specific information about parameters such as the thermal inertia of each envelope element of each building of the whole district. Based on the 14 representative buildings considered, the results show that the greater the facade and roof surface area are, the greater is the TCL difference between the two methodologies, reaching up to 12% in the RAB.2.2AD building. Based on the IG of lighting, occupation, and equipment parameters, the results obtained from the calculations of the DB and DMM are very similar. The difference between the two methodologies does not exceed 6%. Except for one of the representative buildings, the difference in the results for the GS (for 13 buildings) varies between 1% and 11%. Therefore, although this methodology is based on a simplified approach, this validation shows that the difference in the results between DB and DMM does not exceed 11%. Finally, the results for the VL between the two methodologies vary considerably, reaching differences between 13% and 24%. One of the reasons for this difference is that the methodology used by DB, which focuses on a dynamic calculation, considers parameters, such as wind speed and direction or air pressure, which are not considered in the DMM methodology.

Based on the difficulties with respect to the integration of parameters, such as the thermal inertia, wind speed, or the air pressure, into this type of simplified district-scale energy assessment methodology, the variation of the results of 11% (heating), 11% (cooling), and 10% (DHW) obtained from the validation is acceptable.

5.2. Comparison with real consumption

The historical district of Antwerp includes few buildings with monitored gas consumption (339 buildings of 1624). This makes it impossible to carry out a complete validation at the district scale. However, the city of Antwerp has provided natural gas consumption data for buildings that are coloured dark blue in Fig. 6. Therefore, the results related to the useful heating and DHW energy demand could be validated. The cooling demand is out of the scope of this validation because the city does not have information on the electrical consumption of these buildings. Based on data protection policies, the municipality of Antwerp has only been able to

Fig. 5. Percentage difference between the results obtained by both methodologies (the District Mapping Module and the energy simulation software Design Builder) for the 14 representative buildings of the case study. Numeric values for this figure are available in Appendix A1.

Table 12
Validation of natural gas consumption (kWh) of a section of the Historic City of Antwerp for residential and service buildings.

	Antwerp Gas consumption	District Mapping Module (DMM)		Variation
		Useful heating and DHW demand	Gas consumption	
Residential				
Pre - 1945	1,885,784	2,385,043	2,805,933	-48.8%
1970 - 1990	4,969,579	4,226,385	4,972,218	-0.1%
1990 - 2005	2,173,098	2,080,160	2,447,247	-12.6%
Post - 2005	706,059	528,595	621,876	11.9%
TOTAL	9,734,520	9,220,186	10,847,278	-11.4%
Non-residential				
Pre - 1945	6,631,945	7,670,454	9,024,064	-36.1%
1970 - 1990	278,264	124,092	145,991	47.5%
1990 - 2005	74,675	17,543	20,639	72.4%
TOTAL	6,984,885	7,812,090	9,190,694	-31.6%
TOTAL MONITORED	16,719,405	17,032,276	20,037,972	-19.8%

Fig. 6. Buildings with available gas consumption data shaded inside the blue line coloured in dark blue of the Historic City of Antwerp. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Considering that the output of the DEA is the useful energy demand, this work proposes to install a heating and DHW system comprising a natural gas boiler with a nominal efficiency of 0.85. The inclusion of the energy system efficiency allows the conversion of the DEA results into energy consumption and therefore the comparison of the values provided by the case study with values obtained from the DEA (see Table 12).

The variation between the DMM gas consumption assumption and real gas consumption data for residential buildings is 11%. The difference between the results for residential buildings built between 1970–90 and Post-2005 is very small. However, the difference between the results for buildings constructed before 1945 reaches up to 49%. Based on this study, there are several reasons for this large difference: not all buildings are occupied; the inhabitants of these buildings use less heating or some of these buildings have been refurbished, improving their thermal behaviour and considerably reducing the heating energy demand. However, this type of information is usually not available in the main information source of this methodology, that is, the municipal cadastre.

Based on non-residential buildings, it is very difficult to specify parameters, such as the schedule or internal gains, due to the lack of information about the use of some of these buildings, which increases the variation of the results for non-residential buildings to 32%. Again, note that this study does not consider if buildings were

provide gas consumption information aggregated per use and per year of construction, as described in Table 12.

refurbished, their energy efficiency improved, or if their initial use has been modified, thus changing their thermal needs.

6. Discussion

6.1. Sensitivity and uncertainty evaluation

Simulated results often significantly deviate from the monitored values, with discrepancies reaching up to 100% in some cases [56–58]. The quality of the results reflects the precision of the input data. Therefore, it is necessary to adjust these parameters to an adequate level of accuracy. To assess the influence of input data on the results, an analytical calibration method based on continuous updates of the input data is used.

This section presents the sensitivity analysis of different relevant parameters relative to the DMM assessment. Each parameter variation is tested based on the case study of the historical district of Antwerp. For this analysis, three different types of parameters have been evaluated: 1) parameters that are directly related to the building characteristics (window-to-wall ratio, U-values, air change per hours, roof surface, base temperature, and net heated area), 2) parameters that are directly related to the occupant behaviour (schedule, building occupancy, and internal gains), and 3) a parameter depending on the climatology and solar gains.

Sensitivity analysis is performed by varying the value of the input parameters under analysis. The influence of each parameter is calculated using the ‘influence coefficient’ (IC) shown in Eq. (12) [59], where ΔOP and ΔIP are the changes in the output and input, respectively; and $OP_{baseline}$ and $IP_{baseline}$ are the output and input baseline values, respectively.

$$IC = \frac{\Delta OP / OP_{baseline}}{\Delta IP / IP_{baseline}} \quad (12)$$

The influence coefficient is dimensionless and represents the variation in the output due to perturbation in the input. The analysis of coefficient values enables the determination of the parameters with the greatest influence on the results and therefore the detection of possible sources of errors in the considerations and fine-tuning of the energy model.

6.2. Window-to-wall ratio

This study is based on several scientific studies to define window-to-wall ratios (WWR). However, these ratios vary according to factors such as the building typology, location, and climate conditions. Therefore, two new scenarios were defined to consider a variation of $\pm 15\%$ of the initial value proposed in the WWR.

6.3. U-value

To obtain the U-values of the facade, roof, or windows of the existing building stock, different strategies can be applied: 1) *in situ* measurements, 2) search in state or European databases such as the EU building stock observatory [40], or 3) European research projects such as TABULA [60], ENTRANZE [9], or GEOCLUSTER [61]. However, different values can be obtained when analysing and comparing information from different sources. For example, the differences between TABULA [60] and the EU building stock observatory [40] data can reach up to 50%. Because of this variation of the values from different sources, four new scenarios have been added to take these issues into account, assuming that the U-values of the baseline scenario are 15–50% higher and 15–50% lower than initially considered.

6.4. Air change per hour (ACH)

The default values established for the ventilation rates differ between different countries, mainly due to construction traditions and types of construction. Several studies included this parameter in their reports. For example, housing ventilation standards are defined for some of the EU countries in the study developed by the Buildings Performance Institute Europe [62]. Kemna and Acedo report [34] presents average ventilation values for three European zones; different values were established according to the construction period of each building and average European ventilation rates values for different building uses were defined. However, there is no unified database, which classifies the ventilation air change per hour values according to the building construction period, use, and location. The uncertainty associated with this parameter increases due to the lack of uniformity of data related to this parameter. Therefore, two new scenarios have been added to consider these issues. If the air changes per hour differ from initially considered values, a variation of $\pm 15\%$ of the baseline values is proposed.

6.5. Roof area

Because 2D data have been used as input in this energy assessment, the roof area is calculated based on a flat roof. However, this roof area could be more realistic if a 3D data were used. Based on the literature, roofs with pitches between 22° and 50° were identified [63], which leads to a variation of the roof area of 7.8% and 55%, respectively. Therefore, two new scenarios have been added to consider this issue, assuming that the roof area of the baseline scenario is 10% (minimum) or 55% (maximum) higher than the initially calculated value.

6.6. Base temperature

The building and equipment standards assume that the heating base temperature varies between 18°C and 22°C . This range represents a large difference in the energy demand. Overall, the Nordic countries tend to have higher average indoor temperatures than the rest of the EU countries. In Western European countries, the reference indoor temperatures are the lowest and 20°C is commonly used for the simplest calculation procedures. The reference indoor temperature in Southern Europe is 20°C [34]. Other studies [64] including research of almost 300 dwellings suggested that the indoor air temperature fluctuates within a 2° range between $\sim 17.5^\circ\text{C}$ and 19.5°C . Based on the location and use of the building, the cooling base temperatures defined by the standards can vary between 24°C and 26°C . Therefore, four new scenarios have been added to consider these variations, assuming that the heating base temperature is 18°C or 22°C and the cooling base temperature is 24°C or 26°C .

6.7. Net heated area

To carry out a precise energy simulation, it is necessary to consider the NHA instead of the GFA of the building. This correction is made by applying the GHR factor, as explained in Section 3.2.1. However, this information may vary depending on the source. Different ratios were defined for different buildings in several studies [34–37]; there is no unique GHR value for each building use. Therefore, sensitivity analysis will be carried out assuming that the GHR differs from initially considered values. Two new scenarios have been added to consider this issue; a variation of $\pm 15\%$ of the NHR value has been proposed.

Fig. 7. Parameters' influence coefficient for heating (Hea) and cooling (coo) demand in residential (Res), office (Off) and commercial (Com) buildings. Numeric values for this figure are available in [Appendix A2](#).

6.8. Schedule

Heating, cooling, DHW, occupancy, or appliance schedules may significantly change the results for the operational energy use. This parameter adds remarkable uncertainty to the results because it plays a critical role when estimating energy loads of buildings, as shown, for example, by Topouzi [65]. Some studies [66] showed that the influence of inhabitants is much more significant than the variation due to the climate because it is impossible to predict the total energy consumption more accurately than $\pm 15\text{--}20\%$ if the inhabitant behaviour is unknown compared with the consumption obtained from traditional energy calculations. Other research [67] determined that the user behaviour and lifestyle leads to an energy consumption variation of a factor of 2–3 in otherwise identical homes. Indeed, Pettersen [66] and Juodis et al. [68] showed that the user behaviour alters the primary operational energy associated with space heating by $\pm 15\text{--}20\%$. Therefore, new scenarios have been generated to take these issues into account. In this case, the variation must be different for each use due to the differences between the schedules. A variation of ± 2 h has been applied for each building use, except for hotels and health care with 24/7 schedule for which this variation cannot be applied.

6.9. Building occupancy

Although the DMM methodology considers that all buildings of the study are occupied, a considerable amount of buildings are currently unoccupied. For example, the Housing Statistics in the European Union [69] reflect that more than 25% of the dwellings in Belgium are unoccupied. Therefore, a new scenario has been added to consider this issue, assuming that 25% of the buildings are unoccupied.

6.10. Internal gains

Several studies [66] showed that the influence of inhabitants is much more significant than the variation due to the climate because it is impossible to predict the internal gains related to occupancy, appliances, and lighting if the inhabitant behaviour is unknown. Therefore, two new scenarios have been added. A variation

of $\pm 15\%$ of the baseline values is proposed, assuming that the internal gains differ from initially considered values.

6.11. Solar gains

Nowadays, several approaches and algorithms exist to efficiently compute the solar irradiance of each surface of each building considering mutual shadowing. For example, CitySIM [19] uses the Simplified Radiosity Algorithm (SRA) [70] to assess the irradiance incident on the surfaces of each urban area. In addition, the solar irradiance of each surface was obtained within the framework of the EU project 'Cities on Power' by combining the hourly shadowing distribution mask [71] with hourly direct and diffuse irradiation time series for each month [72]. Furthermore, the Solar 3Dcity tool [73] estimates the solar potential of building roof surfaces of a 3D city model stored in CityGML. Wieland and Wendel [74] presented an approach to compute beam and diffuse solar radiation for 3D city models using the CityGML format. Finally, Freitas et al. [75] proposed a 3D approach with feasible tools, such as CityGML and PostGIS, to accomplish solar analysis of urban objects. The methodology defined in this study is limited to 2D assessment, making the assessment of the solar gains of each building surface with the same accuracy as the previous methodologies or studies that are based on a 3D assessment impossible. Therefore, two new scenarios have been added. A variation of $\pm 15\%$ of the baseline values is proposed, assuming that the solar gains differ from initially considered values.

6.12. Sensitivity assessment

The study has been carried out for residential, office, and commercial buildings because they are the most representative of the district, accounting for 52%, 40%, and 5% of the total built area, respectively. Based on this sensitivity analysis, it is possible to analyse the variation of the IC according to the variation of each input parameter.

Fig. 7 shows that the heating base temperature (BT) and heating schedule (SCH) are the parameters with the larger influence on the heating demand assessment of this case study. For example, the results show that the IC for the 'heating base temperature' in an office building is 2.5. The results also show that the IC for

the WWR, roof area (RA), NHA, internal gains (IG), and solar gains (GS) is below 0.5. In fact, it is only 0.16 for the 'WWR' input. If the analysed building is a residential building, the impact of this input parameter is 0.04.

The cooling demand, WWR, cooling BT, and GS are the parameters with the larger influence on the cooling demand assessment. For example, the results show that the IC for the 'cooling base temperature' of a residential building is 4.3. The results also highlight the influence of the GS with an impact of 2.5. The results show that the IC for inputs such as the RA and NHA is less than 0.5. In fact, the impact of the roof area is only 0.19.

The analysis of the influence of all input parameters shows that some of the parameters that have the largest influence are the most difficult to control or determine in buildings with unmonitored energy systems because parameters, such as the base temperature or schedule, for heating and cooling can vary from one building to another or even from one day to another. However, when the energy system is monitored, and the municipality has access to this information, the adaptation of these two parameters can be used to calibrate the model and considerably improve the accuracy of the DMM output. Furthermore, the results show that the influence of parameters, such as WWR and GS, is considerably if the cooling energy demand is assessed by the DMM methodology. Based on the architectural typology, each municipality should calibrate their WWR values because it is difficult to standardise this parameter. Finally, due to the simplification of the DMM methodology, the solar gain parameter does not consider factors such as the orientation of each building or shadows of surrounding buildings. Due to this simplification, the accuracy of the assessment of this parameter using the current version of this methodology is limited. Therefore, future work should focus on the improvement of this parameter.

Once the district model is correctly calibrated, this methodology can be extrapolated to other districts or the entire city to deliver information relevant for the design of the energy plan of the city.

7. Conclusions and future work

This paper proposes a methodology that allows municipalities to carry out energy studies of their existing building stock. The motivation is based on the lack of tools or applications that allow municipalities to evaluate available data and obtain a general energy vision of the city. This methodology is divided into two main blocks: 1) the input data block in which the necessary data sources are obtained and pre-processed, and 2) the district energy assessment block in which the data are processed and the internal energy assessment algorithm is performed to obtain results at the building level for the whole district.

The methodology has been validated based on the application to the historical district of Antwerp. The results of the first validation show that the average difference between the results provided by this methodology and those obtained by Design Builder® is less than 11% for the heating demand, less than 11% for the cooling demand, and less than 10% for the DHW demand. In fact, the validation process shows that the main difference between both methodologies is based on the assessment of two parameters: the thermal conductivity and ventilation losses. The second validation process, which compares the results obtained by this methodology with the real natural gas consumption of 339 buildings of this case study, shows that the variation between the results and the real data for residential buildings is 11%. However, the variation

increases to 32% for tertiary buildings because this study does not consider if buildings have been refurbished, that is, if their energy efficiency was improved or their initial use was modified, changing their thermal needs.

In addition, a sensitivity assessment was proposed in this work including the analysis of the relevance of each input parameter considered by the DMM methodology. Based on the 'influence coefficient', the heating base temperature and heating schedule are the parameters with the larger influence on the heating demand assessment. The cooling demand, WWR, cooling base temperature, and solar gains are the parameters with the larger influence on the cooling demand assessment.

One of the drawbacks of the methodology is its dependency on the input data quality. This methodology intends to simplify the energy assessment with available data, integrating this type of assessments into municipal energy planning processes. Hopefully this will contribute to the improvement of the quality and availability of energy data and encourage the better and wider use of cadastral and energy information. However, it is very difficult to obtain detailed information to define, for example, the specific use of each building because this methodology is based on cadastral information.

In the future, refurbishment strategies should be included in this methodology to consider the age and level of architectural protection of buildings. Other future work might include the calibration of the results through new study cases, the search for new alternatives in case the municipality does not have cadastral data in an accessible format, and improvement of the visualisation of the results to generate a new 3D model for each evaluated district.

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Appendix A1. Numeric values of the results obtained by both methodologies (the District Mapping Module – DMM and the energy simulation software Design Builder – DB) for the 14 representative buildings of the case study

This table shows the following results: annual heating useful energy demand (AHD), annual cooling useful energy demand (ACD), annual Domestic hot water useful energy demand (DHWD), thermal conductivity losses (TCL), internal gains (IG), solar gains (GS) and ventilation losses (VL).

Appendix A2. Numeric values of the parameters' influence coefficient for heating and cooling demand in residential, office and commercial buildings: window to wall ratio (WWR), U-values (U), air change per hours (ACH), roof surface (RA), base temperature (BT), net heated area factor (NHA), schedule (SCH), building occupancy (BO), internal gains (IG) and solar gains (GS)

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.enbuild.2018.05.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2018.05.018).

Building		AHD	ACD	DHWD	TCL	IG	GS	VL
3737081 / RSF.1.2AD	DMM (kWh)	24,798	-1186	2963	-28,815	8907	8985	-15,060
	DB (kWh)	26,311	-1335	3241	-27,303	9467	9299	-19,100
	Difference (%)	5.8%	11.2%	8.6%	-5.5%	5.9%	3.4%	21.2%
3737382 / RSF.1.3AD	DMM (kWh)	19,956	-573	2692	-17,921	8034	3889	-14,483
	DB (kWh)	22,292	-618	2905	-16,005	8504	4023	-19,244
	Difference (%)	10.5%	7.2%	7.3%	-12.0%	5.5%	3.3%	24.7%
3736729 / RAB.1.2AD	DMM (kWh)	42,784	-2508	5491	-52,863	17,053	20,879	-28,832
	DB (kWh)	45,480	-2690	6032	-48,581	18,013	21,607	-36,649
	Difference (%)	5.9%	6.8%	9.0%	-8.8%	5.3%	3.4%	21.3%
3737288 / RAB.1.3AD	DMM (kWh)	38,385	-1559	6389	-40,172	19,625	11,937	-33,181
	DB (kWh)	41,758	-1718	7132	-37,906	20,985	13,069	-42,089
	Difference (%)	8.1%	9.3%	10.4%	-6.0%	6.5%	8.7%	21.2%
3735813 / RAB.2.2AD	DMM (kWh)	48,139	-2654	6450	-57,880	20,145	21,991	-34,060
	DB (kWh)	52,567	-2906	7125	-52,079	21,463	22,762	-42,566
	Difference (%)	8.4%	8.7%	9.5%	-11.1%	6.1%	3.4%	20.0%
3736444 / RAB.2.3AD	DMM (kWh)	94,433	-3978	21,003	-81,134	62,126	25,498	-105,040
	DB (kWh)	100,995	-4396	22,365	-77,282	66,657	32,392	-129,842
	Difference (%)	6.5%	9.5%	6.1%	-5.0%	6.8%	21.3%	19.1%
3735270 / RAB.3.2AD	DMM (kWh)	87,212	-12,595	29,675	-159,152	89,204	81,652	-113,116
	DB (kWh)	90,162	-13,839	32,487	-148,675	93,903	88,912	-136,531
	Difference (%)	3.3%	9.0%	8.7%	-7.0%	5.0%	8.2%	17.1%
3735278 / RAB.3.3AD	DMM (kWh)	10,417	-1492	7408	-15,763	13,232	13,703	-22,913
	DB (kWh)	11,096	-1637	8212	-14,220	13,923	15,062	-27,388
	Difference (%)	6.1%	8.8%	9.8%	-10.8%	5.0%	9.0%	16.3%
3735956 / RAB.4.2AD	DMM (kWh)	16,898	-5244	5180	-26,207	16,053	28,466	-15,833
	DB (kWh)	17,649	-5545	5763	-24,881	16,754	31,753	-18,360
	Difference (%)	4.3%	5.4%	10.1%	-5.3%	4.2%	10.4%	13.8%
5321130 / RAB.4.3AD	DMM (kWh)	11,712	-1582	2726	-22,087	8143	11,218	-10,326
	DB (kWh)	12,711	-1735	2940	-21,872	8571	11,250	-12,888
	Difference (%)	7.9%	8.8%	7.3%	-1.0%	5.0%	0.3%	19.9%
3735359 / OF.1.2AD	DMM (kWh)	22,189	-5772	1208	-74,163	36,324	34,742	-26,695
	DB (kWh)	22,717	-6102	1292	-69,854	38,571	36,297	-33,307
	Difference (%)	2.3%	5.4%	6.5%	-6.2%	5.8%	4.3%	19.9%
3737329 / OF.1.3AD	DMM (kWh)	11,239	-5565	1693	-45,284	52,587	14,549	-38,646
	DB (kWh)	11,947	-5702	1883	-43,215	56,273	15,617	-46,477
	Difference (%)	5.9%	2.4%	10.1%	-4.8%	6.6%	6.8%	16.8%
3736130 / OF.2.2AD	DMM (kWh)	189,855	-94,361	13,528	-333,705	213,242	139,487	-303,693
	DB (kWh)	203,342	-97,462	14,835	-324,882	225,368	141,815	-362,805
	Difference (%)	6.6%	3.2%	8.8%	-2.7%	5.4%	1.6%	16.3%
3736086 / OF.2.3AD	DMM (kWh)	29,075	17,187	6065	113,618	158,928	46,071	137,624
	DB (kWh)	30,680	18,563	6692	106,437	167,467	47,990	158,443
	Difference (%)	5.2%	7.4%	9.4%	-6.7%	5.1%	4.0%	13.1%

Influence coefficient for heating demand assessment

	Residential			Office			Commerce		
	IC	error +	error -	IC	error +	error -	IC	error +	error -
WWR	0.04	4.7E-03	4.7E-03	0.16	5.1E-03	5.1E-03	0.06	1.9E-03	1.9E-03
U	0.84	4.1E-03	4.1E-03	1.11	1.6E-02	1.6E-02	0.53	8.0E-04	8.0E-04
ACH	0.41	7.4E-04	7.4E-04	0.51	4.1E-03	4.1E-03	0.75	1.2E-03	1.2E-03
RA	0.21	8.9E-05	8.9E-05	0.27	6.3E-04	6.3E-04	0.15	1.1E-05	1.1E-05
BT	1.88	8.0E-03	8.0E-03	2.49	3.3E-02	3.3E-02	2.04	5.1E-03	5.1E-03
NHA	0.31	4.7E-02	4.7E-02	0.07	1.2E-02	1.2E-02	0.63	9.5E-02	9.5E-02
SCH	1.26	6.0E-02	6.0E-02	1.90	2.3E-02	2.3E-02	1.38	5.5E-02	5.5E-02
BO	1.00	0.0E+00	0.0E+00	1.00	0.0E+00	0.0E+00	1.00	0.0E+00	0.0E+00
IG	0.11	4.3E-05	4.3E-05	0.44	8.6E-03	8.6E-03	0.14	1.6E-04	1.6E-04
GS	0.14	7.1E-03	7.1E-03	0.18	1.2E-02	1.2E-02	0.14	2.3E-03	2.3E-03

Influence coefficient for cooling demand assessment

	Residential			Office			Commerce		
	IC	error +	error -	IC	error +	error -	IC	error +	error -
WWR	1.98	8.3E-02	8.3E-02	1.50	1.1E-02	1.1E-02	2.33	1.7E-01	1.7E-01
U	1.00	7.5E-02	7.5E-02	0.80	3.7E-02	3.7E-02	0.97	7.2E-02	7.2E-02
ACH	0.44	1.7E-02	1.7E-02	0.36	9.7E-03	9.7E-03	1.22	1.2E-01	1.2E-01
RA	0.18	2.7E-03	2.7E-03	0.18	1.8E-03	1.8E-03	0.19	2.6E-03	2.6E-03
BT	4.30	4.0E-01	4.0E-01	3.91	1.6E-01	1.6E-01	4.10	6.0E-01	6.0E-01
NHA	0.23	2.7E-02	2.7E-02	0.39	6.2E-02	6.2E-02	0.56	3.9E-02	3.9E-02
SCH	0.76	0.0E+00	0.0E+00	0.21	5.0E-03	5.0E-03	0.17	1.3E-02	1.3E-02
BO	1.00	0.0E+00	0.0E+00	1.00	0.0E+00	0.0E+00	1.00	0.0E+00	0.0E+00
IG	0.21	7.2E-03	7.2E-03	0.74	2.2E-02	2.2E-02	0.66	2.4E-02	2.4E-02
GS	2.21	1.2E-01	1.2E-01	1.90	2.6E-02	2.6E-02	2.51	2.1E-01	2.1E-01

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